

Funded by
the European Union

MYRTUS

Multi-layer 360° dYnamic orchestration and interopeRable design environmenT for compute-continUum Systems

Deliverable: **D11.2 Dissemination and Communication Plan v1**

Due date of deliverable: (31-08-2024)

Actual submission date: (28-08-2024)

Start date of Project: 01 January 2024

Duration: 36 months

Responsible: Andrés Otero (UPM)

Revision: draft

Dissemination level		
PU	Public	x
DEC		
SEN		

DOCUMENT INFO

Author

Author	Company	E-mail
Andres Otero	UPM	joseandres.otero@upm.es
Tiziana Fanni	ABI	tiziana.fanni@abinsula.com
Alessandra Bagnato	SOFT	alessandra.bagnato@docaposte.fr
Jeronimo Castrillon	TUD	jeronimo.castrillon@tu-dresden.de
Danilo Pani	UNICA	danilo.pani@unica.it
Giulia Sedda	UNICA	giulia.sedda@unica.it
Andreas Kercek	LAKE	andreas.kercek@lakeside-labs.com
Melanie Schranz	LAKE	schranz@lakeside-labs.com
Francesco Regazzoni	USI	francesco.regazzoni@usi.ch
Julio de Oliveira	TNO	julio.deoliveirafilho@tno.nl
Luca Castello	ARK	luca.castello@arubakube.cloud
Mauro Fadda	UNISS	mfadda1@uniss.it
Bart Driessen	TNO	bart.driessen@tno.nl

Document history

Document version #	Date	Change
0.1	17/05/2024	First Draft of D11.2
0.2	23/05/2024	Table of contents and initial structure shared with all the partners request individual contributions.
0.3	08/07/2024	Consolidated version of the deliverable with all the inputs by partners.
0.4	24/07/2024	Consolidated draft submitted to the internal reviewers
0.5	23/08/2024	Consolidated draft after the internal reviews

0.6	23/08/2024	Version ready to submit
-----	------------	-------------------------

Document data

Keywords	Communication, Dissemination
Editor Address data	Name: Andrés Otero Partner: UPM Address: José Gutiérrez Abascal, 2. 28006, Madrid, Spain Phone: +34 676 62 46 17 email: joseandres.otero@upm.es

Funded by the European Union, by grant No. 101135183. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Table of Contents

1 Executive Summary	5
1.1 Related Documents	5
1.2 Structure of the Document	6
2 Dissemination and Communication Strategy	6
2.1 Communication and Dissemination Goals in MYRTUS	7
2.2 Identification of the Target Groups	8
2.3 Methodology for Communication and Dissemination	22
Branding and graphic design	22
Generation of Dissemination Materials	23
Continuous Feedback and Advice from Dissemination Activities	23
2.4 Open Access Policy	23
3 Digital Channels	24
3.1 Project Website	24
3.2 Partners' websites	24
3.3 Social Networks	26
4 Media and Press Releases	26
4.1 Traditional channels	26
4.2 Scientific press	26
5 Scientific Publications	27
5.1 Scientific Publications Plans	27
5.2 Conferences and Workshops	30
6 Fairs and Events	33
6.1 Participation in Fairs and External Events as a Consortium	33
6.2 Individual participation in other events	33
6.3 Organization of Events	34
7 Joint dissemination with other projects	35
8 Monitoring and Success Performance Indicators	36
9 Conclusions	37
10 References	37

1 Executive Summary

The deliverable *D11.2 - Dissemination and Communication Plan v1* is an R type (Document, Report), and it provides the first version of the dissemination and communication plan of the MYRTUS project. It includes the activities covered in WP11.

D11.2	WP	Lead	Type	Month
Dissemination and Communication Plan v1	WP11 - Communication and Dissemination	UPM	R	M8

R: Report type

This report defines a roadmap for guiding all Communication and Dissemination (C&D) activities within the project, ensuring that all target groups identified during the proposal stage are reached. This deliverable marks the first stage of an incremental process that will continuously monitor the project's dissemination and communication results, measured by associated key performance indicators (KPIs) and the partners' adherence to this plan. A new version of the plan (D12.4) will be provided by Month 22, considering the results at the end of Phase 1 of the project, the feedback from the first review, and contributions from third parties, including communities and other initiatives. The plan integrates all individual dissemination and communication efforts, offering a coherent strategy to impact the target communities effectively.

Table 1 – Deliverable D11.2- Dissemination and Communication Plan v1

<p>D11.2- Dissemination and Communication Plan v1 – M8 – Tasks Involved: T11.1 (M1-M36) - Communication [SOFT(L), ALL] T11.2 (M1-M36) - Dissemination [UPM(L), ALL]</p>

1.1 Related Documents

This deliverable closely relates to the following documents:

- **D13.1 - Project quality handbook:** Includes the templates for generating dissemination material, the logos, and the internal communication tools, among others.
- **D11.1 – Project website and social media account:** Describes the channels for reaching the MYRTUS target audience and objectives, including traditional approaches, such as the project website and social media (LinkedIn, X, and YouTube). These tools will be of significant importance for the project's C&D activities.
- **D12.2 - Exploitation, Standardisation, and Open Source Plan v1:** Exploitation and Dissemination activities are closely related, being addressed together thoroughly, in WPs 11 and 12.

1.2 Structure of the Document

The rest of this deliverable is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 2: Dissemination and communication strategy** - Provides an overview of the high-level communication strategy, setting the goals, the target groups, and the methodology that will guide the whole plan.
- **Chapter 3: Digital Channels for MYRTUS dissemination** - Including websites and social networks.
- **Chapter 4: Media and Press releases** - Including traditional channels and non-scientific focused press.
- **Chapter 5: Scientific publications** – Ranging from journals to conferences and workshops.
- **Chapter 6: Fairs and Events** - Both at the consortium and partner levels. Particular emphasis will be put on events organised by the MYRTUS partners.
- **Chapter 7. Joint dissemination with other projects** - Where specific actions are described to foster collaborations with other sister projects funded by the HORIZON Europe called "*Cognitive Computing Continuum: Intelligence and Automation for More Efficient Data Processing*".
- **Chapter 8. Monitoring and Success Performance Indicators** - Describes the methodology to be followed to monitor the evolution of the adherence of the project partners to the C&D plan and the list of metrics selected to report the results.

2 Dissemination and Communication Strategy

The goal of the WP11 in MYRTUS is to effectively disseminate the MYRTUS activities and results across all target groups. To guarantee the success of these activities, this plan is provided, including all the required measures to ensure that C&D activities align with the project plans and the detailed actions and resources needed to implement the C&D strategy effectively. Finally, metrics will be established to monitor the effectiveness of C&D activities.

The communication and dissemination actions outlined in this plan focus on sharing information about the project and its results with scientific, industrial, and societal audiences. In MYRTUS, dissemination and communication activities are strictly linked to exploitation, and the overall targets are illustrated in Figure 2. Some of these targets (“switched off” in the figure) are primarily exploitation targets, and communication and dissemination actions towards them are meant mainly for the use of results (see deliverable D12.2 for details). The rest of the targets (“highlighted” in the figure) are primarily dissemination and communication targets.

Figure 2- MYRTUS Dimension highlighting main dissemination and communication targets

Please, note that only external communication channels are described in this document. Internal communication within the consortium will follow the channels and tools described in the *Project Quality Handbook*, along with the procedures established at the coordination and management levels. All the partners will rely on the mailing list to share novel opportunities for communication and dissemination that are not anticipated in this plan.

2.1 Communication and Dissemination Goals in MYRTUS

The goals for the C&D plan will be related to the KPIs provided in Chapter 8 of this deliverable. All the activities envisaged in this document are oriented to achieve the expected impact of MYRTUS:

- At the Scientific level:
 - Create new knowledge in the computing continuum domain, with methodologies and tools for node execution and processing portability over edge-fog-cloud, including dynamic and seamless orchestration.
 - Become a reference in the computing continuum.
 - Follow-up research and projects beyond MYRTUS.
- At the economic and technological level:
 - Overcome vendor/platform lock-in.
 - 15 external startups and SMEs adopt MYRTUS technologies, reducing development time and cost.
 - MYRTUS industrial partners enrich their business offerings and attract key world-leading partners.
- At the social level:
 - Induce positive changes of habit in the society through human-centres CPS.
 - Guarantee capillarity rehabilitation services and equitable access to care.
 - Decrease mortality on the road by making intersections safer.
 - Contribute to the CO2 emission reduction.

2.2 Identification of the Target Groups

Effective communication and dissemination requires clearly identifying the target groups. A preliminary version of the MYRTUS dimension was already provided in the proposal and included in the Grant Agreement (Table 8). This list of identified target communities has been reviewed and updated as part of this C&D plan. The relevance of each community and the main scientific and industrial collaborations significant to the project are detailed in Tables 2.2.a, 2.2.b, and 2.2.c.

Table 2.2.a – Relevant Communities per partner (s)

Domain	Partner (s)	Community	Detail and relevance to MYRTUS
High-Performance Computing (HPC), embedded, edge, and cloud computing	ABI, TUD, UNICA, UNISS, UPM, USI	HiPEAC [1] stands for High-Performance, Edge, and Cloud computing. With over 2000 specialists, this network is a focal point for dissemination, training, and collaboration activities in Europe for researchers and industry related to computing systems.	Edge and Cloud technologies are certainly of extreme interest to MYRTUS, and the HiPEAC events, magazines, and channels are highly relevant. Indeed, the MYRTUS consortium has identified the HiPEAC conference (normally held in January/February) as a possible location for the project final event. Five MYRTUS partners are members of HiPEAC, and other partners, such as ABI, are highly active in the HiPEAC community even though they are not formal members.
Electronic Components and System (ECS) domain.	ABI, UNICA, UNISS, UPM	INSIDE [2], the European research and innovation community is active in Intelligent Digital Systems and the ECS domain.	INSIDE IA counts more than 200 key players all over Europe, who create opportunities for the academy and industry to meet and create synergies. MYRTUS has already started exploiting INSIDE events, magazines, and communication to raise awareness of the project.
			Prof. Francesca Palumbo has been organising a Summer School on CPS sponsored by INSIDE since 2017 [3]. This school centred on

			CPS technologies, has already been identified as an excellent medium for disseminating MYRTUS technologies.
Cloud Systems, Secure Systems, and SoS	ARK	Distributed Systems and Cloud-related communities	Arubakube actively participates in the most important events and conferences about Distributed Systems and Cloud Native initiatives, such as KubeCon, Kubernetes Communities Days, Cloud Conf, or ContainerDay, creating interesting opportunities for MYRTUS dissemination.
	HIRO	Kinetic Edge Alliance (KEA) [4] is the alliance of industry-leading companies. KEA collaborates to facilitate the design, deployment, and operation of edge computing solutions. KEA brings together diverse expertise and technologies to foster innovation and accelerate the adoption of edge computing.	KEA's role is to ensure seamless integration and interoperability of HIRO's micro data centers within the broader fog/edge computing framework. This collaboration enhances the scalability, reliability, and security of fog/edge services in MYRTUS.

	HIRO	<p>Open Grid Alliance (OGA) [5] is an initiative focused on evolving the internet to support distributed computing and real-time applications through grid computing. Catalysed by the emergence of fog/edge infrastructure, 5G networks, and billions of IoT devices, the grid is the next step in the evolution of the Internet. Globally distributed, the Grid weaves together a public and private fabric of computing, data, and intelligence to enable contextually aware, immersive applications at the fog/edge, on demand.</p>	<p>HIRO can leverage the Open Grid Alliance to enhance the fog layer with robust grid computing capabilities. OGA's focus on distributed computing aligns with MYRTUS's goals of dynamic orchestration and interoperability across the compute continuum.</p> <p>By integrating OGA principles, HIRO's Fog Microdatacenters can efficiently manage distributed workloads, support real-time applications, and ensure seamless data flow. This collaboration provides the foundational grid infrastructure, enabling MYRTUS to achieve scalable, flexible, and high-performance fog/edge solutions.</p>
	LAKE	Swarm Community	<p>This includes researchers around Europe who deal with the main principles of swarm algorithm modelling (Dorigo, Hamann, di Caro, etc.), typically reaching them through publications and conferences.</p>
	KCL	Machine Learning (ML), edge Artificial Intelligence (AI), and AI for 6G communities	<p>KCL has major expertise in ML, including synchronised Federated Learning and multi-agent Reinforcement Learning (RL) for edge and distributed intelligence.</p>
	USI	Security, System Design, and Design Automation communities.	<p>USI has strong expertise in security, from the design of cryptographic algorithms to the implementation in embedded and cyber-physical systems and in the</p>

			automation of secure system design.
	TNO, ARK (Aruba), SOFT (Docaposte)	Gaia-X [6] involves an international alliance of more than 500 institutions. It promotes a set of standards for the portability, interoperability, and interconnection of the infrastructure, the applications, and the data.	MYRTUS will guarantee compatibility with Gaia-X, ensuring the necessary flexibility to provide competitive solutions for data sovereignty in Europe.
	SOFT, TNO	Cloud Modeling, Cloud Application Modelling, and Execution Language (CAMEL) is akin to the topology and orchestration specification for cloud Applications [7], which allows users to specify the components comprising the topology of cloud-based applications and the processes for their orchestration. However, while TOSCA supports the specification of types and templates only, CAMEL supports the specification of types, templates, and instances. TOSCA Community is potentially a very good target.	SOFT has major expertise in Cloud Modeling, in particular, related to the CAMEL is a multi-domain-specific language allowing users to specify multiple aspects/domains related to multi-/cross-cloud applications, such as the domains of deployment, requirement, metric, scalability, security, organisation, and execution. That has evolved to a full-fledged cloud (application) modelling language thanks to its adoption in other European projects, including MORPHEMIC ¹ and MELODIC ² .

¹ MORPHEMIC Project: <https://www.morphemic.cloud/>

² MELODIC Project: <https://melodic.cloud/>

	MYRTUS at the project level	<p>The European Cloud Edge IoT Initiative (EU-CEI) [8] aims to realise a pathway for the understanding and development of the Cloud, Edge, and IoT Continuum by promoting cooperation between a wide range of research projects, developers and suppliers, business users, and potential adopters of this new technological paradigm. The EU-CEI Initiative is now a collaborative ecosystem that counts over 50 member projects and initiatives.</p>	<p>During the first month of the project's life, MYRTUS was invited to join the EU-CEI initiative, and it has been an active member of the community since then.</p>
CPS, Embedded systems, and IoT Domains	TUD, UNISS, UNICA	<p>The Dataflow Model of Computation (MoC) community includes many projects and groups that study dataflow-based approaches for modelling, simulation, and design of concurrent, real-time embedded systems. Ptolemy [9] (University of Berkeley) is one of the most relevant projects in this community.</p>	<p>In MYRTUS, we leverage and extend existing MoCs. MoCs have a long history (>30 years) and are developed in a small but elite community. Engaging with the community in conferences or research stays will increase MYRTUS's visibility and improve the quality of its results.</p>
	UPM	<p>Open HW community: RISC-V International, CHIPS Alliance, and the OpenHW Group</p> <p>Spanish RISC-V Network and Spanish Open Hardware Alliance (SOHA)</p>	<p>RISC-V is an open ISA supported by RISC-V International that consists of a basic instruction set that is modularly extensible by a series of dedicated instruction extensions for specialised application domains. In MYRTUS, novel adaptive RISC-V processors that leverage run-time FPGA</p>

			reconfiguration will be developed, enabling on-demand computing.
	TUD, UNICA, UPM	MLIR (Multi-Level Intermediate Representation) [10] is a novel approach to building reusable and extensible compiler infrastructure.	The dialects developed in MYRTUS will be presented at MLIR meetings and discussed with our international networks of researchers on high-level compilation abstractions. This will make the dialects better reusable outside MYRTUS and thus increase our impact.
Healthcare Use Case	UNICA	Italian National Bioengineering Group (GNB)	The new paradigm of multiscale collaborative rehabilitation will be presented and discussed with the experts in the field, including the biannual event of the scientific society. The PhD school, annually organised by GNB, is also an important opportunity for student exchange and interactions.
	UNICA	Italian Society of Movement Analysis in Clinics (SIAMOC [11])	The clinicians' perspective is the key to assessing the proposed approach in human rehabilitation scenarios. In October 2025, UNICA will co-organize the 2025 edition of the annual SIAMOC conference.
	UNICA	IEEE Sensors Council	UNICA contributed with Prof. Danilo Pani to the birth of the Italian Chapter of the IEEE Sensors Council [12]. The Chapter is very active in proposing different activities for the associates, including lectures and events.

Mobility Use Case	TNO, CRF	Automotive, including ID4Mobility [13]	Promotion of the Myrtus project. This is a good opportunity to get feedback on the proposed technology and its integration challenges.
-------------------	----------	--	--

Table 2.2.b – Scientific Collaborations per partner (s)

<i>External Institution</i>	<i>Partner (s)</i>	<i>Detail and relevance to MYRTUS</i>
EPFL, Embedded System Lab team Prof. Atienza (CH)	UPM	The physical design of an ASIC prototype of the node featured a RISC-V core with the CGRA attached. This technology will be the core of one of the MYRTUS edge nodes.
Barcelona Supercomputing Center team Francisco Cazorla (ES)	UPM, HIRO.	RISC-V advances focused on application areas with safety-critical demands. Highly related to the MYRTUS edge node.
National Institute of Microelectronics team Lluís Terés (ES)	UPM	Collaboration in the physical implementation of RISC-V based nodes. Related to the MYRTUS edge node.
University of Maryland, team Prof. Bhattacharyya (US)	TUD, UNISS, UNICA	Dataflow modelling for Node-level optimization tools (MDC for UNICA and UNISS). Related to the MYRTUS edge node.

<p>INSA RENNES team Prof. Nezan (FR)</p>	<p>TUD, UNISS, UNICA, ABI</p>	<p>UNISS and UNICA already worked with the group of INSA Rennes on dataflow model of computation oriented studies. TUD has done so as well, with a recent book chapter on dataflow programming flows the Handbook of Computer Architecture, Springer (2023). There is a plan to continue this cooperation in connection with the MLIR-related tasks in WP7-8.</p> <p>ABI worked with INSA Rennes in past projects and they continue looking for new opportunities to collaborate. Currently, discussions are ongoing to evaluate the involvement of ABI in the current ITN Rising Stars³, of which INSA Rennes is a partner. Related to WP7-8.</p>
<p>University of California, Berkeley team Prof. Edward A. Lee (US)</p>	<p>TUD</p>	<p>TUD has been collaborating with the group of Prof. E. A. Lee since 2018. The Reactor model and the Lingua Franca framework stem from this collaboration, which will be continued in the context of the work in WP7-8.</p>
<p>University of California, Berkeley Prof. Sangiovanni-Vincentelli's group (US)</p>	<p>TUD, UNICA</p>	<p>Some of the collaborative work of TUD with Prof. E. A. Lee involves Prof. Sangiovanni-Vincentelli. Moreover, Prof. Francesca Palumbo is traditionally organising a Summer School on CPS since 2017, where Prof. Sangiovanni-Vincentelli has always been present to provide the latest insights on CPS research and industry trends. The current goal is to write, as a school outcome but certainly thanks also to MYRTUS studies, a vision paper on CPS in the era of continuum.</p>

³ <https://www.risingstars-project.eu/>

<p>European Organization for Nuclear Research (CERN)</p>	<p>HIRO</p>	<p>The European Organization for Nuclear Research is known for its pioneering work in particle physics and advanced computing technologies.</p> <p>CERN's expertise can be used in high-performance computing and data management. CERN's advanced computing infrastructure and experience with large-scale data processing can enhance HIRO's Fog Microdatacenters' capabilities, ensuring efficient and secure data handling in the fog.</p> <p>The partnership with CERN ensures that MYRTUS benefits from state-of-the-art innovations in computing and data science, facilitating robust and scalable edge solutions.</p>
<p>Center for Tactile Internet in Dresden (CeTI), 6G-life hub (DE)</p>	<p>TUD</p>	<p>CeTI and the 6G-life hub are two large research centres in Dresden, each involving upwards of 60 principal investigators. The work developed in MYRTUS is highly related to the need for efficient, time-critical, and safety-critical applications that these centres address. Prof. Castrillon is a principal investigator of the 6G-life hub and collaborates with several PIs of both centres. Collaborations will be centred, specifically, on time-deterministic distributed computing for robotics.</p>
<p>Politecnico di Milano team Prof. Giacomo Verticale (IT)</p>	<p>UNISS</p>	<p>Ongoing collaboration on activities about orchestration in the cloud-to-edge continuum. Related to WPs 6 and 7 MYRTUS activities.</p>

University of Genova team Prof. Maura Casadio (IT)	UNICA	Ongoing collaboration on virtual reality for rehabilitation, based on visual feedback distortion. The group of prof. Casadio is renowned for its high-quality and highly focused research on rehabilitation technologies, including robotic rehabilitation and virtual reality. Related to MYRTUS Healthcare Use Case.
Politecnico di Torino, team Prof. Andrea Cereatti (IT)	UNICA	Ongoing collaboration on telerehabilitation systems based on measuring human motion parameters with wearable and contactless sensors. Related to MYRTUS Healthcare Use Case.
Carnegie Mellon University Qatar Prof. Gianni A. di Caro (QA)	LAKE	Collaboration and joint papers regarding applications of swarm intelligence. Related to WPs 7 and 8 MYRTUS activities.
University of Durham Prof. Farshad Arvin (UK)	LAKE	Collaboration and joint papers regarding applications of swarm intelligence. Related to WPs 7 and 8 MYRTUS activities.
University of Konstanz Prof. Heiko Hamann (DE)	LAKE	Collaboration and joint papers regarding applications of swarm intelligence. Related to WPs 7 and 8 MYRTUS activities.
University of Magdeburg Prof. Sanaz Mosthagim (DE)	LAKE	Member of Lakeside Labs Advisory Board.

Table 2.2.c – Active Industrial Collaborations per partner (s)

External Institution	Partner (s)	Detail and relevance to MYRTUS
Deutsche Telecom, Magenta, Telefonica, Ericsson, Turkcell, and Retelit, among other telecom providers.	LAKE, HIRO	HIRO is active in the development of edge technologies in collaboration with these telecom providers, as well as with hardware and software industry leaders (e.g., ARM, INTEL, CODEPLAY) and leading R&D institutes (e.g., BSC, CERN). In the context of MYRTUS, HIRO's involvement focuses on enhancing fog infrastructure capabilities, ensuring high performance and reliability of fog microdatacenters. This includes leveraging telecom partners' communication technologies to enable real-time data processing and low-latency connectivity, which are critical for the efficient operation of the compute continuum envisioned by MYRTUS.
Infineon	LAKE	The main relevance is their usage of the fog layer inside of the industrial environment and how to coordinate data processing on the edge layer.
NXP, Thales, Bombardier	TNO	These industrial partners often work with TNO on edge-oriented solutions and technologies that require or benefit from Myrtus's orchestration strategies. Within these contexts, the projects' solutions will be slowly transferred to the industry.
Topcon-Tierra, Applix, Seat Pagine Gialle, Samsung, Tata Consulting	ABI	ICT companies are already among the Abinsula customers; therefore, a direct channel exists to present the MYRTUS technologies to them.

<p>Nokia, Huawei, Ericsson, Samsung, Nokia, and Toshiba</p>	<p>KCL</p>	<p>In the next two years, KCL will develop an open-edge infrastructure with edge intelligence for robotics applications funded through the 6 million Horizon Europe VERGE project and 12 million UK DCMS REASON project, in close collaboration with these companies and some world-leading universities.</p> <p>KCL will exploit its collaborations with major telco and consumer electronics companies to sell possible patents.</p>
<p>Aruba group</p>	<p>ARK</p>	<p>ArubaKube will exploit its knowledge within the entire Aruba Group.</p> <p>Beyond that, many different European IT companies and cloud providers will be reached, as well as technology consortiums like Bi-Rex and more.</p>
<p>ARM, INTEL, CODEPLAY</p>	<p>HIRO</p>	<p>HIRO collaborates with ARM, INTEL, and CODEPLAY to enhance the capabilities of edge and fog computing infrastructures. This collaboration focuses on integrating advanced hardware and software solutions to ensure high performance, scalability, and reliability of fog micro data centers. Within MYRTUS, these partnerships are crucial for developing the compute continuum by leveraging cutting-edge technologies in processors, compilers, and system architectures. The combined expertise of these industry leaders helps HIRO to deliver robust edge solutions that support real-time data processing, low-latency connectivity, and secure data handling, aligning with the project's goals of creating a dynamic and efficient compute continuum.</p>

<p>Nvision, Tecnica Automotive Barcelona, Silemelife, CLUE Aerospace</p>	<p>UPM</p>	<p>Spanish companies in sectors such as IoT, automotive, and aerospace participating in the Spanish PERTE CHIP program, with a strong focus on RISC-V-based SoCs. Synergies with the MYRTUS node development.</p>
<p>Airbus CRISA</p>	<p>UPM</p>	<p>Active collaborations with AIRBUS CRISA in the context of BSc/MSc/PhD programs related to RISC-V for critical systems. Synergies with the MYRTUS node development.</p>
<p>Indra</p>	<p>UPM</p>	<p>UPM is collaborating with Indra on the development of the FCAS (Future Aircraft Air Systems), which involves adaptive platforms based on RISC-V. As part of the INDRA-UPM Chair on Microelectronics, Indra, and UPM are also collaborating on the development of RISC-V technologies for safety-critical applications.</p>
<p>AMD</p>	<p>TUD</p>	<p>TUD collaborates with AMD to develop high-level compilers for heterogeneous computing systems (AI engines, FPGAs, GPUs). This gives TUD preferential access to new computer architectures, allowing for early testing of the tools developed in MYRTUS.</p>
<p>Ortopedia Chessa s.r.l.</p>	<p>UNICA</p>	<p>The partnership aims to promote, develop and consolidate opportunities and initiatives of collaboration in the field of wearable technologies for prosthetics, orthoses, and rehabilitation.</p>

Medical Concept Lab	UNICA	<p>The partnership aims to promote, develop, and consolidate opportunities and initiatives of collaboration in the following areas:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Medical devices; • Electromedical devices and systems; • Systems for telemonitoring, telehealth, telemedicine, and teleassistance; • Algorithms for the analysis of electromedical signals for clinical applications; • Cardiac endocavitary electrophysiology.
YouandTech	UNICA	<p>The partnership aims to promote, develop, and consolidate opportunities and initiatives of collaboration in the following areas:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Telemedicine, telemonitoring, and teleassistance; • Devices, sensors, and technologies for biosignal recording and biofeedback; • Decision support and signal processing technologies.
Spes Medica s.r.l.	UNICA	<p>The partnership aims to promote, develop, and consolidate opportunities and initiatives for collaboration on innovative technologies for the realisation of biopotential electrodes.</p>
221e	UNICA	<p>The partnership aims to promote, develop and consolidate opportunities and initiatives of collaboration in the following areas:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Innovative technologies for the realisation of sensors and their integration in smart projects;

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experimental tests and development of prototypes.
Systematic	SOFT	<p>Systematic [16], the European Deep Tech hub, has brought together and led, since its creation in 2005, a community of nearly 900 members dedicated to Deep Tech (Open Source, Digital Trust, Digital Infrastructure and IoT, Digital Engineering, Data Science & AI, Photonics). Systematic thus addresses 3 major economic and societal challenges: the digital transformation of territories, industry, and services as well as society. The Cluster accelerates digital projects through collaborative innovation, the development of SMEs, networking, and business sourcing in the sectors of the future: energy, telecoms, health, transport, information systems, and manufacturing plants. future, digital city, security.</p>
Axis	CRF	<p>Presentation of MYRTUS and, more generally, integration of IP cameras in the computing continuum.</p>

2.3 Methodology for Communication and Dissemination

Branding and graphic design

The common visual identity has been defined and reported in the *Project Handbook* and is available for all the partners in the shared repository, together with the associated templates. The project logo is shown in Figure 2.3.

Figure 2.3- MYRTUS Logo

Generation of Dissemination Materials

Project communication, dissemination, and visibility is ruled by the Grant Agreement, article 17. The statement and disclaimer for external communication are provided in the file MYRTUS acks.

During the second phase of the project, Abinsula (project coordinator) will collaborate with UPM (WP11 Leader) and SOFT (WP12 Leader) to coordinate the preparation of promotional material in digital and hardcopy form.

Continuous Feedback and Advice from Dissemination Activities

Communication and dissemination in MYRTUS are envisioned as a closed-loop process. This approach ensures that MYRTUS researchers not only reach target groups to maximise project impact but also continuously gather feedback on the project's technical activities and their reception by the scientific, industrial, and societal communities. A key focus will be on the acceptance of corrections or improvements to the project's technical developments.

This feedback process in MYRTUS is systematically planned. After conferences and other discussion events, where informal feedback is gathered, any relevant comments identified by a MYRTUS researcher will be documented and shared with the entire consortium via email. If deemed necessary, the project coordinators can introduce a specific agenda item in the MYRTUS monthly meetings to address this feedback.

A feedback procedure based on online forms will be implemented for other dissemination activities, such as seminars and tutorials. This will be used to enhance the quality of the dissemination content continually.

2.4 Open Access Policy

MYRTUS is aligned with the Open Science principles promoted by the European Commission, which improve the diffusion of generated knowledge and data, foster open cooperative work, and maintain a solid adherence to the FAIR principles [17]. As derived from these principles,

scientific publications in MYRTUS will follow the Open Access guidelines for Horizon Europe to ensure transparency of the processes and outcomes of research and disseminate new knowledge to foster open science.

The Zenodo MYRTUS data repository is available: <https://zenodo.org/communities/myrtus/>

All the partners share the responsibility of uploading all the created dissemination content to this repository, recognizing the activities and benefits Zenodo offers, including the direct link to the EU open repository.

3 Digital Channels

The actions envisaged by the Myrtus consortium through digital channels are gathered in this chapter.

3.1 Project Website

The MYRTUS website, as outlined in deliverable D11.1, will serve as the central hub for all project activities, including public deliverables, publications, and other tangible results. Enhanced with high-quality visual design and illustrations, the website makes MYRTUS more engaging and memorable.

Figure 3.1- MYRTUS Web Site

3.2 Partners' websites

Most of the partners have used the websites of their respective organizations to announce the kick-off of the project. A list with some of the links is provided in Table 3.2.

Table 3.2 – Mention to MYRTUS on each partner website

<i>Partner</i>	<i>Announcement on the website</i>
ABI	Inclusion in the list of research projects on the Abinsula website: https://abinsula.com/myrtus/
TUD	Since the start of MYRTUS, the project has been listed on the webpage of the Chair for Compiler Construction at TUD, under “Major Collaborations”: https://cfaed.tu-dresden.de/cc-collaborations
UNISS	Publication of the KO Meeting on the institutional website: https://www.uniss.it/it/eventi/progetto-horizon-europe-myrtus
UNISS	Inclusion in the list of funded projects on the institutional website https://www.uniss.it/it/ricerca/finanziamenti-la-ricerca/finanziamenti-europei/progetti-di-ricerca-europei
UNICA	Inclusion in the list of funded projects on the MeDSP Lab website https://sites.unica.it/medsp/projects/
KCL	Inclusion in the list of funded projects on the institutional website: https://www.kcl.ac.uk/news/kings-engineer-awarded-horizon-europe-grant-to-build-connected-future-for-healthcare-and-smart-cities
SOFT	Inclusion in the list of research projects on the Softam R&D website: https://www.softeam-rd.eu/projects/myrtus-multi-layer-360-dynamic-orchestration-and-interoperable-design-envi

LAKE	Inclusion in the list of funded projects on the organisational website (Available until mid of July 2024): https://www.lakeside-labs.com/research/projects-and-funding/
CRF	Inclusion in the list of research projects on the CRF web site: https://www.crf.canon.fr/AboutCRF_en.html
UPM	Reference to the face-to-face General Assembly celebrated in Madrid: https://www.industriales.upm.es/noticias/asamblea-general-del-proyecto-myrtus/

3.3 Social Networks

Social networks, particularly LinkedIn, will replace traditional newsletters, which are now less effective at reaching larger audiences. To increase engagement, we will publish monthly posts focusing on the project's technical aspects, timed to coincide with relevant accepted publications. Based on positive interactions, selected posts will be expanded into longer LinkedIn articles, with an expectation of producing 3-4 such articles per year. In turn, X will be adopted to reach a broader audience (beyond the professional scope of LinkedIn). The content shared in both social networks will be equivalent, but adapted, when needed, to this more generalistic scope.

Further details on the presence and activities of MYRTUS in social media (particularly X and LinkedIn) are provided in D11.1.

4 Media and Press Releases

4.1 Traditional channels

Traditional media is considered to inform society beyond the scientific community, reaching a more general audience. MYRTUS consortium will promote the submission of press releases coinciding with relevant events in the project, such as the Kick-off Meeting, published in La Nuova Sardegna (based on the original text by UNISS⁴), or the intermediate and final project events.

4.2 Scientific press

⁴ <https://www.uniss.it/it/eventi/progetto-horizon-europe-myrtus>

MYRTUS will also target non-scientific magazines generally addressed to academic and industrial communities. In particular, two main magazines have already been identified:

- **Inside Magazine:** this magazine targets the INSIDE IA community. It is generally promoted through the Inside’s digital channels and is mainly distributed digital copy. However, during physical events organised by INSIDE, hard copies of the Magazine are available. Contributions related to MYRTUS have already been published in the INSIDE IA Magazine #6 (February 2024)⁵ and #7 (June 2024)⁶.
- **HiPEAC Info:** The HiPEAC Info magazine is a quarterly publication providing the latest news on the activities within the European HiPEAC network, as well as activities on high-performance embedded architectures and compilers at large. The magazine is sent to more than 500 researchers from academia and industry and company managers in Europe, America, and Asia.

5 Scientific Publications

The actions related to scientific publications are provided in this chapter.

5.1 Scientific Publications Plans

The following journals are envisaged for the publication of MYRTUS results in Table 5.1.

Table 5.1 – List of scientific journals targeting for publication by each partner

Journal ⁷	Partner (s)	Target Community	MYRTUS Pillar
Journal of Systems Architecture: Embedded Software Design IF 2023: 3.7 - Q1	UNICA, UPM, TUD	Embedded and Reconfigurable Systems; Compilers; architectures; HPC	Pillar 1 and Pillar 3
ACM Transactions on Reconfigurable Technology and Systems IF 2023: 3.1 - Q2			
ACM Transactions on Architecture and Code Optimization IF 2023: 1.5 - Q2			

⁵ <https://intranet.inside-association.eu/publication/download/inside-magazine-6.pdf>

⁶ <https://intranet.inside-association.eu/publication/download/inside-magazine-7.pdf>

⁷ Impact Factor (IF) as reported by the Journal Citation Reports (JCR) and the highest quartile ranking achieved in any of the categories where the journal is indexed.

<p>IEEE Embedded Systems Letters</p> <p>IF 2023: 1.7 - Q3</p>			
<p>IEEE Transactions on Computer-Aided Design of Integrated Circuits & Systems</p> <p>IF 2023: 2.7 - Q2</p>			
<p>IEEE Computer Architecture Letters</p> <p>IF 2023: 1.4 - Q4</p>			
<p>IEEE Transactions on Computers</p> <p>IF 2023: 3.6 - Q2</p>			
<p>Elsevier Computer Networks Journal</p> <p>IF 2023: 4.4 - Q1</p>	UNISS	Cloud to Edge Distributed Systems	Pillar 2
<p>IEEE Systems Journal</p> <p>IF 2023: 4.0 - Q1</p>			
<p>IEEE Transactions on Cloud Computing</p> <p>IF 2023: 5.3 - Q1</p>			
<p>IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications</p> <p>IF 2023: 13.8 - Q1</p>	KCL	Communications	Pillar 2
<p>IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications</p> <p>IF 2023: 8.9 - Q1</p>			

IEEE Transactions on Communications IF 2023: 7.2 - Q1			
IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology IF 2023: 6.1 - Q1			
IEEE Internet of Things Journal IF 2023: 8.2 - Q1			
IEEE Transactions on Neural Systems and Rehabilitation Engineering IF 2023: 4.8 - Q1	UNICA	Neuroengineering and Rehabilitation	Healthcare Use Case
Journal of NeuroEngineering and Rehabilitation IF 2023: 5.2 - Q1			
The Ada User Journal Not in JCR	SOFT	Ada Programming Language	Pillar 3
ACM SIGAda Ada Letters Not in JCR			
Swarm and evolutionary computation, Elsevier IF 2023: 8.2 - Q1	LAKE	Self-organising systems and swarm intelligence	Pillar 1
Swarm Intelligence Journal, Springer IF 2023: 2.1 - Q3			

IACR Transactions on Cryptographic Hardware and Embedded Systems Not in JCR	USI	Security	Pillar 2
IACR Transactions on Symmetric Cryptology IF 2023: 1.7 - Q2			

5.2 Conferences and Workshops

The MYRTUS consortium plans to attend the following conferences and workshops individually to stay in contact with the related communities, to disseminate the project with the attendees, and when applicable, to present original research works:

Table 5.2 – Participation in Conferences and Workshops by each partner

<i>Conferences, Workshop or fair</i>	<i>Partner (s)</i>	<i>Target Community</i>	<i>Yearly scheduled by</i>
Challenges and New Approaches for Dependable and Cyber-Physical System Engineering (DeCPS 2024) Co-located with the 28th Ada-Europe International Conference on Reliable Software Technologies (AEIC 2024), June 11-14	SOFT	Artificial Intelligence for CPS Model-based system engineering for CPS	Q2
International Conference on Fog and Mobile Edge Computing (FMEC)	ARK	Cloud and edge	Q3
USENIX Symposium on Operating Systems Design and Implementation (OSDI)	ARK	Embedded systems	Q2
Reconfigurable Architectures Workshop (RAW)	UPM, UNICA, UNISS	Reconfigurable systems	Q2

ACM International Conference on Computing Frontiers (CF)	UPM, UNICA, UNISS, USI	Embedded systems and HPC	Q2
International Conference on Embedded Computer Systems: Architectures, Modeling and Simulation (SAMOS)	UPM, UNICA, UNISS, USI	Embedded systems and EDA	Q3
Design, Automation and Test in Europe Conference (DATE)	TUD, UPM, USI	Embedded, EDA	Q2
Design Automation Conference (DAC)	TUD, USI	Embedded, EDA	Q3
Embedded Systems Week (ESWeek)	TUD, USI	Embedded	Q3
The High Performance Edge And Cloud computing (HiPEAC) Conference	TUD, USI	HPC, embedded, cloud and edge	Q1
ACM/IEEE International Conference on Computer-Aided Design (ICCAD)	TUD, USI	EDA, Security	Q3
International Conference on Consumer Electronics (ICCE)	UNISS	Embedded	Q1
Rehab Week	UNICA	Rehabilitation	Q2

Annual Congress of the Italian Society of Clinical Movement Analysis (SIAMOC)	UNICA	Rehabilitation	Q4
Congress of the National Group of Bioengineering (GNB)	UNICA	Biomedical engineering	Q2
IEEE Biomedical Circuits and Systems Conference (BIOCAS)	UNICA	Biomedical circuits and systems	Q3
IEEE Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society (EMBC)	UNICA	Biomedical engineering	Q2
IEEE International Conference on Communications (ICC)	KCL	Communication	Q2
IEEE GlobeCom	KCL	Communication	Q4
IEEE International Conference on Autonomic Computing and Self-Organizing Systems (ACSOS)	LAKE	Self-organizing Systems	Q2
IEEE International Conference on Advanced Networks and Telecommunications Systems (ANTS)	LAKE	Swarm intelligence	Q2
International Conference on Adaptive and Self-Adaptive Systems and Applications (ADAPTIVE)	LAKE	Adaptive Systems	Q4
Conference on Cryptographic Hardware and Embedded Systems (CHES)	USI	Security	Q3
Real World Crypto	USI	Security	Q2

ID4Mobility	CRF	Mobility, ITS	2026
-------------	-----	---------------	------

Some special sessions in conferences have been also identified, targeting European Projects, where the evolution of the consortium as a whole can be presented. Some examples are the following publications:

- Computing Frontiers 2024
- DSD 2024 Special Session on “European Projects in Digital System Design”

6 Fairs and Events

6.1 Participation in Fairs and External Events as a Consortium

The following actions are envisaged as a consortium:

- Intermediate event at the CPS Summer School organized by UNISS, including an exhibition to present the intermediate results of the project, and a technical session showing MYRTUS technology.
- Final scientific event at HiPEAC, to present the final results to the scientific community.
- Final Industrial event at Embedded World to present the final results to the industrial community.

6.2 Individual participation in other events

Apart from the expected project-wise events, some partners will participate in local events of different natures to reach a more general audience.

Table 6.2 – List of other events in which MYRTUS partners will participate

Partner	Event	Relevance to Myrtus
UNICA UNISS	SHARPER Night (European Researchers Night) 2024	Display the MYRTUS results in a stand as part of the initiatives for the SHARPER Night. The event allows researchers to showcase their work to the general public.
TUD	OUTPUT.DD and Lange Nacht der Wissenschaften	Display MYRTUS results in established science communication events in Dresden and Germany.
UNICA	Maker Faire (Rome)	Showcase of the health UC with MYRTUS technologies

LAKE	Lange Nacht der Forschung	Show the scientific results of MYRTUS to the general public.
REPLY	Reply XChange Events and VR and Gaming fair (to identify)	Showcase VR APP of Myrtus Healthcare UC
UPM	Industriales Research Meeting (IRM)	This annual conference is celebrated at the ETSI Industriales of the UPM, where the research activity carried out by Professors and PhD affiliated with the school is presented to the rest of the academic community. The scientific results of MYRTUS are also shown to the general public.

6.3 Organization of Events

Most of the dissemination actions and events in this plan involve multiple partners, highlighting the collaborative nature of the MYRTUS project. Additionally, some partners are involved in organizing long-standing events, providing excellent opportunities to engage with well-established communities that may find MYRTUS results valuable.

International CPS Summer School: The International CPS Summer School (UNISS) is an annual one-week event that targets students, research scientists, and R&D experts from academia and industry who want to learn about CPS engineering and applications. The school started in 2017 and covers all the design phases of CPSs, starting from the conception of the idea down to the definition of the final system and will discuss the key challenges (including adaptivity support, modelling, and security), presenting state-of-the-art tools and methods, also allowing participants to play with industrial and academic design environments. Lectures and tutorials are given by academics (e.g., Prof. Alberto Sangiovanni-Vincentelli, UC Berkeley, Prof. Hironori Kasahara, Waseda University) and industrial speakers (e.g., Dr Danilo Pau, STMicroelectronics, Dr. Paolo Azzoni, Eurotech/INSIDE). The director of the School since its origin is Prof. Francesca Palumbo, and almost all editions so far have taken place in the north of Sardinia.

In 2024 the school will take place in Alghero, in the facilities of the University of Sassari and, apart from Prof Palumbo. Also, Prof. Francesco Regazzoni (USI), Prof. Mauro Fadda (UNISS), Dr. Claudio Rubattu (UNISS), and Dr. Francesco Ratto (UNICA) from the MYRTUS consortium are involved in the organisation committee. Dr. Claudio Rubattu (UNISS) and Dr. Francesco Ratto (UNICA) are going to give a tutorial titled “Adaptive CNN execution on edge FPGAs” which involves the technologies jointly developed by UNISS and UNICA in WP3 and WP7. Moreover, in 2025 we have already planned to have the MYRTUS intermediate communication and dissemination event co-located with the CPS Summer School.

CEI Annual Meeting: The CEI annual meeting (UPM) is a two-day meeting focused on relevant technology trends (e.g., “Open Hardware & RISC-V” for the 2022 edition,” Challenges in Microelectronics” for 2024) that hosts: 1) workshops/tutorials on hot topics (e.g., “Building

custom RISC-V Systems on Chip with open-source tools"); 2) keynotes and/or round tables (e.g., with members of the Barcelona Supercomputing Centre and the National Microelectronics Institute); 3) technical sessions, poster sessions, and networking occasion of their research activities.

The next event will be organised in May 2025, and all the students involved in MYRTUS will participate with a poster. Besides, the RISC-V based node and the required infrastructure to adapt it to the cloud-edge continuum will be the target of at least one oral presentation next year.

Lakeside Research Days: The bi-annual Lakeside Research Days (LAKE) is a four-day workshop on topics like self-organisation in particular fields of application. Limited by 50 participants, including invited experts, local professors, and young researchers, discuss and elaborate ideas in the field of Self-Organizing Systems. The main emphasis of the workshop is on soliciting discussions and creating new ideas regarding topics related to self-organising systems. The event greatly supports scientific exchange, networking, the establishment of international collaborations, and joint research projects. The following video gives a nice impression of the Research Days: <https://youtu.be/3DPas4L1ov0>

The next event will take place in July 2025. The organisation will start in autumn 2025, with the umbrella topic "Swarms in Industry". Regarding MYRTUS, the 360° vision of the architecture and how this consideration benefits from swarm intelligence approaches will be presented.

Reply XChange: The XChange event by Reply is an annual conference organised by Reply that focuses on technological innovation, digital transformation, and emerging trends in the IT sector. This event serves as a significant platform for industry professionals, clients, partners, and technology experts to gather, share knowledge, and discuss the latest advancements and best practices. The event features presentations by industry leaders, technology experts, and senior managers, offering insights on current topics and future perspectives. Attendees can participate in hands-on workshops and interactive sessions where they delve into specific technological topics, experiment with new solutions and engage in discussions. Live demonstrations of innovative projects and technological solutions developed by Reply and its partners showcase practical applications and case studies, providing real-world context to the discussions. Networking opportunities abound, allowing attendees to meet, exchange ideas, and establish professional connections with peers, industry experts, and representatives from partner companies. Additionally, the expo area features exhibition spaces where partner companies and sponsors present their products and services, offering further opportunities for discovery and interaction.

Overall, the XChange event by Reply is a key event for anyone interested in technological advancements and innovation, providing a stimulating environment for learning, collaboration, and the development of new business opportunities.

7 Joint dissemination with other projects

HYPER-AI project⁸: This project, funded in the same call of MYRTUS, aims at overcoming network continuum challenges by integrating smart virtual nodes from the cloud, edge, and

⁸ <https://hyper-ai-project.eu/>

IoT to optimise intensive data processing. Its goal is to revolutionise big data processing applications with self-abstracted and self-coordinated cloud-to-edge resources and it also fosters the co-creating of technologies and tools for the cognitive computing continuum. For this reason, HYPER-AI is promoting actions to join the efforts of 7 different EU projects (HYPER-AI, INTEND, EMPYREAN, ENACT, MYRTUS, Swarmchestrator, and COGNETS) funded by the HORIZON Europe call "Cognitive Computing Continuum: Intelligence and Automation for More Efficient Data Processing" to promote the use of the edge-cloud Continuum as a secure, autonomous, reliable, and self-managing computing resource. The first action MYRTUS has been invited to join will be a webinar: Get to know the research initiatives about Cognitive Computing Continuum: Intelligence and automation for more efficient data processing⁹.

The webinar aims to highlight the collaborative efforts and breakthroughs in integrating the IoT-Edge-Cloud continuum, AI-driven resource management, and hyper-distributed computing ecosystems. MYRTUS will contribute by presenting its three main technical pillars.

8 Monitoring and Success Performance Indicators

The KPIs for the C&D activities were already included in the proposal and confirmed in the Grant Agreement, from which the following table is extracted. This plan will maintain the same goals as the target. Please, notice that Period 1 refers to "During the project + 1 year", and Period 2 refers to "Period 1 + First 5 years after project end".

Table 8 – KPIs for the different MYRTUS C&D Tools

C&D Tool	Key Performance Indicators		
	Period 1 (Expected)	Period 2 (Expected)	Verification
Project's Website	7500 page views	13000 page views	Google Analytics
Social Media Presence	300 posts 600 followers	400 posts 1200 followers	Social media analytics
Videos	10 YouTube videos, 500 visualisations	5000 visualisations	YouTube analytics
Promotional material in digital and hardcopy form	1000 recipients (digital and hardcopy)	2000 recipients (only digital)	Project reporting

⁹<https://hyper-ai-project.eu/events/webinar-get-know-research-initiatives-about-cognitive-computing-continuum-intelligence>

Publications in scientific journals/ conferences	50 articles 75 citations	250 citations	Google Scholar, Scopus, DBLP
Official EU Key Tools. Articles in EU magazines.	Use of the 4 Key Tools. 3 articles published at EU magazines	6 articles published at EU magazines.	Project reporting
Open-source tools	300 downloads overall 30 contributors	900 downloads overall 100 contributors	Downloads Contributors
Project public events*	3 physical events 30 attendees*	--	Project reporting
Partner public events	3 physical events 30 attendees*	30 events 30 attendees*	Project reporting
External events participation	40 physical events 30 attendees*	60 events 30 attendees*	Project reporting

* Average number of attendees per event

The evolution of the KPIs will be evaluated at every General Assembly Meeting, held every six months, as part of the review of WP 11 activities.

9 Conclusions

This document outlines the MYRTUS plan for communication and dissemination activities. The planned actions are categorised by the type of channel used, including digital channels, media and press, scientific publications, and fairs and events. Through these actions, the consortium aims to reach all the target groups identified earlier in this document. The plan's effectiveness will be assessed using a set of KPIs, with results reported in the D11.3 and D11.5 deliverables. An updated version of the plan, intended to keep updated the project's communication and dissemination activities, will be provided in D11.4.

10 References

[1] <https://www.hipeac.net/>

[2] <https://www.inside-association.eu/>

- [3] [Home - CPS Summer School \(cpsschool.eu\)](http://cpsschool.eu)
- [4] [The Kinetic Edge Alliance | Vapor IO](#)
- [5] [Open Grid Alliance](#)
- [6] [Home - Gaia-X: A Federated Secure Data Infrastructure](#)
- [7] <https://www.oasis-open.org/committees/tosca/>
- [10] [Home - EUCloudEdgeIoT](#)
- [11] <https://ptolemy.berkeley.edu/people/index.htm>
- [12] <https://mlir.llvm.org/>
- [13] <https://www.siamoc.it/>
- [14] [Home - IEEE Italy Sensors Chapter](#)
- [15] [ID4Mobility | innovation & industrial mobility ecosystem](#)
- [16] <https://systematic-paris-region.org/nos-missions/>
- [17] [Open Data, Software and Code Guidelines | Open Research Europe \(europa.eu\)](#)